

Exponential non-Physics Learning Rate Optimiser

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Abstract

Choosing learning rate involves heuristics and some of the learning rates are chosen as a rule of thumb. Otherwise, another common practice is to use Hessians for each layer to estimate the learning rate. This is computationally intensive. Instead of these extremes, with just an estimate of the learning rate, an exponential exploration is employed in which, gradient is computed using backpropagation and learning rate is considered using two models: One using the current learning rate and the second one using an experimental learning rate and then considering the next learning rate based on the data of these two learning rates.

The software program-code is available here:
<https://github.com/PrasadNR/momentum-check>

1 Introduction

One of the main reasons why this research paper is being authored is to objectively identify the reason as to why we have to resort to either a thumb rule, based on physics, that is supposed to work for all types of data-sets or compute Hessians. Also, there seems to be no optimiser that uses no physics. There is no optimiser that uses the concept of exploration and exploitation (reinforcement learning). Partially Observable Markov Decision Process is part of the proposed optimiser model that is used as we do not observe loss of the entire epoch.

2 Prior Work

There exists no prior work as it relates to exponential optimiser. Blind Descent algorithm's idea of "we can choose to accept or reject an update" is used for the learning rate.[1] This allows us to experiment with multiple learning rates and using only the learning rate that works. We can try a learning rate and if it is high, we can reduce that learning rate without having to update the model with "bad" learning rate. PyTorch's popular optimisers include the following:[2]

- **Adadelta**[5]: This uses some type of decay of history of gradients mean. The proposed algorithm requires no history.
- **Adagrad**[6]: This uses some type of decay too.
- **Adam**[7], **NAdam**[8], **RAdam**[9] and **AdamW**[10]: This uses moments which are updated over time.
- **LBFGS**[11]: This uses memory intensive history unlike the proposed algorithm. It uses line search.
- **RMSProp**[12] and **Rprop**[13]: Moving average of squared gradients

Only Adam (and AdamW) seems to be remotely close to the proposed algorithm. But, that seems to depend upon the gradients of the learning, doesn't use RL-like algorithm and has a lot of hyper-parameters that can make the exponential learning rate ineffective if suboptimal hyper-parameters are chosen. The proposed model that is used is like that of finite-horizon POMDP.[14] So, there are two losses of two models which are tracked. The state-space is binary for both of those losses (they either increase or decrease). The action-space is about choosing one of the two models. The episode is over a meta-batch.

Some of the listed optimisers seem to fail when default parameters are used. They don't seem to help the model train at all. Every batch may have different data that does not have to be like that of statistics of physics. May be this is one of the reasons why such optimisers fail. This is true even for data like that of EMNIST (and MNIST). Also, the guidelines for the process of choosing hyperparameters of these optimisers seem to about complete trial and error.

3 Proposed algorithm

The crux of this is this: Use two learning rates for each batch and train two models. Adjust the learning rate based on the data of both learning rates. Also, choose one of the two models (the better of the two). The truth table of this is like this:

Lesser loss?			
LR	experimental LR	output	copy
--	-----	-----	----
True	True	lr * eta_rate	experimental model
True	False	lr	-
False	True	lr / eta_rate	-
False	False	lr / eta_rate	-

There are three phrases that we need to introduce for this:

- *Initial LR*: The initial learning rate to start the optimisation with.
- *Eta rate*: The rate at which the exponential adjustment of learning rate works. It is greater than 1.
- *Meta-batch size*: Chunk size. Meta-batch (or chunk) is the batch of batches.

The idea is that we try out experimental LR which is eta_rate times LR. We also try out LR. We have two models for the same. For each meta-batch, if we consider the reduced truth table, it is this:

- If the loss of the experimental model reduces, we will use the experimental model (and learning rate of the experimental model which is eta rate times the current LR)
- If the loss of the current model increases, learning rate is reduced to current LR / eta rate.

4 Experiments

Two datasets are being used: MNIST[3] and EMNIST[4]. No data augmentation is done. For all the experiments, the following are used:

	MNIST	EMNIST
N epochs	3	3
LR (initial)	0.025	0.01
η_{rate}	1.25	1.5
Batch size	16	32
Meta-batch size	32	64

```
pythonProject - Version control - Current File - 25 11:04 AM
Mnist.py common.py momentum_check.py plots.py

class CNN(torch.nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(CNN, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = torch.nn.Conv2d(1, out_channels=16, kernel_size=5, padding=2)
        self.pool1 = torch.nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2, padding=1)
        self.conv2 = torch.nn.Conv2d(16, out_channels=8, kernel_size=5, padding=1)
        self.pool2 = torch.nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2, padding=1)
        self.fc1 = torch.nn.Linear(8 * 7 * 7, out_features=128)
        self.fc2 = torch.nn.Linear(out_features=128, out_features=10)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = self.conv1(x)
        x = self.pool1(x)
        x = self.conv2(x)
        x = self.pool2(x)
        x = self.fc1(x.view(-1, 8 * 7 * 7))
        x = self.fc2(x)
        return x

class MNIST_CNN(torch.nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(MNIST_CNN, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = torch.nn.Conv2d(1, out_channels=16, kernel_size=5, padding=1)
        self.pool1 = torch.nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2, padding=1)
        self.conv2 = torch.nn.Conv2d(16, out_channels=8, kernel_size=5, padding=1)
        self.pool2 = torch.nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2, padding=1)
        self.fc1 = torch.nn.Linear(8 * 7 * 7, out_features=128)
        self.fc2 = torch.nn.Linear(out_features=128, out_features=62)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = self.conv1(x)
        x = self.pool1(x)
        x = self.conv2(x)
        x = self.pool2(x)
        x = self.fc1(x.view(-1, 8 * 7 * 7))
        x = self.fc2(x)
```

Figure 1: CNN models used

4.1 MNIST and EMNIST prior work

So, if we see this, many of the optimisers seem to be working properly. But, we can see that RMSprop and Rprop seem to have problems with convergence. Rprop seems to stop learning after a very few meta-batches. The CNN models used are simple as the focus is about the optimisers and not the CNN model/s itself. Both CNN models are as in the image.

We can see the losses of RMSprop and Rprop. RMSprop does not seem to have a decreasing loss after an epoch. Rprop seems to have increasing loss. This is the reason why a new optimiser may be needed that adapts to the loss data without any assumptions about the statistics.

Figure 2: MNIST test accuracy and loss

Figure 3: EMNIST test accuracy and loss

4.2 LR init

For MNIST, we see that for wide range of LR init, it seems to converge: 0.001 to 0.05. Note that 0.1 seems to be having some problems. This may have to do with data-set itself. For EMNIST, we see that 0.001 to 0.05 works. In fact, for 0.001, we can see that the EMNIST training happens in about half a epoch.

We can see patterns in the learning rate. It increases the learning rate when needed and vice versa. MNIST seems to have large adaptive learning rate problems with higher initial learning rate of 2 and 3 (and even 0.1 for some reason).

Regarding training and testing loss, we see that the training loss and testing loss have similar patterns. But, the training loss seems to have spikes (both MNIST and EMNIST; see EMNIST ones) while the testing loss seems to have a "smooth" loss reduction. This means that the optimiser is prone to over-fitting (given that it chooses really nice locally optimal learning rate).

If we see the test accuracy, MNIST seems to have problems with 0.5, 2 and 3 learning rates as they are very high. Also, if we see, MNIST has problems with initial learning rate of both high learning rates like 0.0001 and 1. If we see the EMNIST test accuracy, 0.5, 1 and 2 cause the model to not learn. Even 0.25 seems to cause the model to not learn properly.

Figure 4: LR init

4.3 η_{rate}

If we see the eta rate, this algorithm seems to work with a very wide range of eta rates. MNIST one seems to work properly. Except very high eta rate of 4, it seems to converge properly if we see the MNIST plots. Both very low eta rate and very high eta rate of MNIST seem to cause the convergence to be rough.

All eta rates of the plots seem to work if we use EMNIST data. 1.125 to 2, all of them seem to work. Also, any spikes in the training loss are reversed in the subsequent meta-batches.

Figure 5: η_{rate}

4.4 Batch size

As we can see, this is almost independent of the batch size. If we see MNIST, the learning rate seems to be between 0 and 0.2. If we see EMNIST, the learning rate seems to be between 0 and 0.4.

Regarding the test accuracy, if we see very high batch sizes, the training seems to take more number of meta batches (like 64 and 128 of MNIST). If we see EMNIST, we can see that the lower batch size like 16 can also cause the training to use more meta batches. EMNIST also shows that the higher batch sizes like 128 and 256 can cause the training to use more meta batches. 64 batch size of MNIST is causing a minor spike at the end of third epoch.

If we see MNIST test loss, all batch sizes seem to work. The same goes for EMNIST as well (even if the means of the losses are shifted up; we are only trying to minimise loss). The train loss seems to have a lot of spikes. This spike problem is not so if we use large batch sizes.

Figure 6: Batch size

4.5 Meta-batch size

The train loss seems to have a lot of spikes. But, that does not seem to be causing any problems with the test accuracy (because, the better model is chosen at the end of every meta batch). MNIST 16 meta-batch size seems to have a spike and this may be because of over-fitting. All other MNIST meta batch sizes seem to be fine. MNIST learning rate is between 0 and 0.35 which is fine.

EMNIST seems to be working for all of the meta-batch sizes. If we see the meta-batch size of 512, we see a spike by about the end of first epoch. This may be because of over-fitting. But, even then, it seems to converge better.

Figure 7: Meta-batch size

5 Conclusions and future work

The proposed robust algorithm uses no physics. So, the expectation is that it will work for data-sets that do not have nice patterns like that of many of the images. The proposed algorithm has over-fitting problems. A better regularisation is needed for this. Also, a reinforcement learning algorithm may be better (instead of two models only). A better use of Partially Observable Markov Decision Process is needed.

Also, an aspect is to use variable batch size, meta-batch size and η_{rate} and making the state-space and action-space sparse and relative if we happen to use reinforcement learning. Also, a distributed compute process is another aspect that can be considered as we have embarrassingly parallel models.

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